

OPTIMAL INVENTORY POLICY WITH PRICE-DEPENDENT DEMAND AND VARIABLE DETERIORATION RATE ALSO DELT WITH TRADE CREDIT

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we developed an inventory model for an optimal payment policy for deteriorating items under the influence of trade credit. Demand rate of the product is considered as the function of selling price. Here, we consider the deteriorating item that follows three-parameter Weibull distribution deterioration. Finally, the optimal solution is illustrated with help of numerical example and the sensitivity analysis is carried out with respect to different parameters.

Introduction and literature review: One of the most unrealistic assumptions in traditional inventory models was that items preserved their physical characteristics while they were kept stored in inventory. However, the deteriorating items are subject to a continuous loss in their masses or utilities throughout their lifetime due to decay, damage, spoilage and plenty of other reasons. Owing to this fact, controlling and maintaining inventory of deteriorating items becomes an important problem for decision makers in modern organization. In the traditional EOQ model, it is assumed that the customer must pay for the items purchased as soon as the items are received. In practice, a supplier permits a fixed period for the settling the account and usually there is no charge if the outstanding amount is settled within the allowed fixed period. Goyal (1985) first studied an EOQ model under the condition of permissible delay in payments. Chand and Ward (1987) analyzed Goyal's problem under different assumptions of the

classical EOQ model, obtaining different result. Aggarwal and Jaggi (1995) then extended Goyal's model for deteriorating items. Jamal et al. (1997) further generalized the model to allow shortages. Sarker et al. (2000) developed a model for optimal cycle and payment times for a retailer in a deteriorating items inventory situation where a supplier allows a specified credit period to the retailer for payment without penalty. Teng (2002) extended Goyal's model by considering the difference between unit price and unit cost, and assumed that it makes economic sense for a well established buyer to order less quantity but increase the times of placing order so as to take the benefits from the permissible delay. Huang (2005) investigated the optimal cycle time and optimal payment time under the trade credit and cash discount policies. Ouyang et al. (2008) demonstrated that the entire supply chain could achieve a significant profit increase by linking trade credit and freight rate policies. De and Goswami (2009) considered a probabilistic EOQ model for deteriorating items under trade credit. Chang et al. (2009) developed a mathematical model to determine the optimal payment time and replenishment cycle for deteriorating items. Tsao (2010) determined two-phase pricing and inventory decisions for deteriorating and fashion goods under trade credit conditions. Skouri et al. (2011) developed an order level inventory model for deteriorating items with general ramp-type demand rate under conditions of permissible delay in payment and shortages allowed with partial backlogging. Mahata (2012) investigated the optimal retailer's replenishment decision for deteriorating items under two level of trade credit policy to reflect supply chain management situation within the economic production quantity framework. Zhong and Zhou (2013) developed an integrated model with trade credit where a supplier sells a single product through a retailer who has limited storage space and faces an inventory dependent end demand. Jagii et al (2013) developed a replenishment decision under two-level credit policy for flexible credit linked demand. Trade credit affects the conduct of business significantly for many reasons. For the supplier who offers trade credit, it is an effective means of price discrimination as well as efficient method to stimulate the demand of his products. Bera et al(2013) presented an optimal partial backordering two-storage inventory model for deteriorating items with variable demand and the goal of this work is to develop an inventory model (deterministic) for single deteriorating items having two separate storage facilities (owned and rented warehouse) due to limited capacity of the existing storage (owned warehouse). Sivashankari and Panayappan (2014) developed a production inventory model for two levels production with defective items and incorporating multi-delivery policy and Krishnamoorthi et al (2014) presented an inventory model for product life cycle (growth stage) with defective items and shortages. In real life, deterioration takes place when inventory physically present in stock. Deterioration is defined as damage, decay, spoilage, obsolescence, evaporation, loss of marginal value or utility of goods. Deterioration cannot be neglected in inventory problem such as foodstuffs, chemicals, IC chip, electronic components, pharmaceuticals, radioactive substances, etc. An exponentially decaying inventory was developed by Ghare and Schrader (1963). Covert and Philip (1973) extended Ghare and Scharader's constant deterioration rate to a two-parameter

Weibull distribution whereas Chakrabarty et al. (1998) used the three-parameter Weibull distribution deterioration in their inventory. These investigations were further followed by several researchers as Chang and Dye (2001), Chang (2004), Yang and Wee (2006), Taso and Sheen (2007), Li and Mao (2009), Chung et al. (2011), Widyadana and Wee (2012). Dem and Singh (2013) presented a production model for ameliorating items with quality consideration we create a production model for ameliorating inventory system with time-varying demand. Here, the term 'amelioration' refers to improvement in the goods which causes value increase or benefit from the amount used at the time. Lawrence et al (2013) developed a discrete time deteriorating inventory system with geometric lead time and address the situation in which the perishable items are packaged and stored in a suitable and controlled environment so that items in the packets do not perish over time. Darwish and Aldaihani (2013) developed an optimal wholesale price for producer in supply chain under newsboy environment. Alkhedher and Darwish (2013) developed an optimal process mean for a stochastic inventory model under service level constraint. Lawrence et al (2013) developed a discrete time deteriorating inventory system with geometric lead time and address the situation in which the perishable items are packaged and stored in a suitable and controlled environment so that items in the packets do not perish over time. Pricing of the product is a major strategy of any wholesaler or retailer. Consequently, to sell more amounts, wholesaler or retailer reduces the selling price of the product. Therefore, demand of the product increases by reducing the selling price. The first attempt to analyze a price function for perishable items was done by Eilon and Mallaya (1966). They assumed a maximum lifetime for an item. Kim et al. (1995) studied joint price and lot size determination problems for deteriorating products with constant rate of deterioration. Abad (1996) considered the dynamic pricing and lot-sizing problem of perishable goods with shortages under partial backlogging of demand. Abad (2001) discussed a pricing and lot-sizing problem for a product with variable rate of deterioration, allowing shortages with partial backlogging. He also developed the theories for the general forms of time variable decay rate and price-dependent demand rate. Hou and Lin (2006) developed an EOQ model for deteriorating items with price and stock-dependent demand rate. Begum et al. (2010) developed an EOQ model for varying deteriorating items with Weibull distribution and price-dependent demand. They assumed that the demand and deterioration rates are continuous and differentiable function of price and time. Begum et al. (2012) developed an order level inventory system for deteriorating items with demand rate as function of selling price. They assumed that perishable items that follow a three-parameter Weibull distribution deterioration. Gupta and Singh (2013) developed an integrated inventory model with fuzzy variables, three-parameter Weibull deterioration and variable holding cost under inflation. Form above survey it observed that there is very little contribution of researchers in Operations Research to discuss the functional relationship between demand rate and selling price of items in contrast of supply chain management. In the literature referring to models with trade credit period in payments, mostly assumed that there is no deterioration or constant rate of deterioration. Also assumed that demand rate is either constant or as continuous differentiable function of time. However, it is observed that demand for new

brand of consumers' goods coming to the market depends upon the selling price. Retailers attract the customer for that type of product with the help of selling price and try to make familiar with that product. In this article, we have developed an inventory model to obtain the optimal payment time and replenishment cycle with the following realistic phenomenon:

- a. Supplier provides trade credit period to his/her retailer to settle the dues. After due date, supplier charges higher rate to the unpaid amount.
- b. Three parameters Weibull distribution deterioration is considered.
- c. Demand is non-linear function of the selling of the selling price.

2. Notations and Assumptions:

2.1: Following notations has been used for the development of mathematical model:

P is the selling price per unit

The demand rate is a function of selling price. We assume it as follows: $D(P) = (aP^{-b})$, where $a, b > 0$

H is the holding cost per unit time.

C is the purchasing cost per unit time.

S is the replenishment cost per order

T is the length of inventory cycle

The deterioration rate $\theta(t) = \alpha\beta(t - \gamma)^{\beta-1}e^{-\alpha(t-\gamma)^\beta}$ where α (scale parameter) > 0 ,

β (shape parameter) > 0 and γ (position parameter) > 0

I_p is the interest charged per \$ in stocks per year by the supplier

I_e is the interest earned per \$ in stocks per year

K is the payment time to the supplier

2.2: The proposed model has been developed under the following assumptions:

1. Demand rate for the item is nonlinear function of selling price.
2. Shortages are not allowed.
3. Replenishment is instantaneous.
4. During the trade credit period 'M', the account is not settled, and generated sales revenue is deposited in account to earn interest. At the end of the trade credit, retailers have two choices when they pay the supplier:
 - a. They can pay off at the end of trade credit period 'M'

- b. They can pay off at any time between ‘M’ and ‘T’.
- 5. The instantaneous rate of deterioration of the inventory is followed by a three-parameter Weibull distribution.

3. Modelling and Analysis: The level of inventory $I(t)$ gradually decreases mainly to meet the demand and partially due to the deterioration. Hence, the variation of inventory with respect to time can be described by the following differential equation:

$$\frac{dI(t)}{dt} + \theta(t)I(t) = -D(P), \quad 0 \leq t \leq T \quad \dots (1)$$

With the boundary conditions:

$$I(0)=Q \text{ and } I(T)=0$$

The solution of equation (1) under the boundary condition $I(0)=Q$, is given by

$$I(t) = Qe^{-\alpha(t-\gamma)^\beta} - aP^{-b} \left(\int_0^t e^{\alpha(t-\gamma)^\beta} dt \right) e^{-\alpha(t-\gamma)^\beta} \quad \dots (2)$$

Using the boundary condition $I(T)=0$ in equation (2), we get

$$Q = aP^{-b} \left(\int_0^T e^{\alpha(t-\gamma)^\beta} dt \right) \quad \dots (3)$$

On putting the value of ‘Q’ from equation (3) in equation (2), we get

$$I(t) = aP^{-b} \left(\int_t^T e^{\alpha(t-\gamma)^\beta} dt \right) e^{-\alpha(t-\gamma)^\beta} \quad \dots (4)$$

Now, we illustrate the calculation of different associated cost of inventory step by step as follows:

Cost of placing order=S

$$\text{Cost of purchasing} = CQ = CaP^{-b} \left[T^2 + \frac{\alpha T}{1+\beta} \{ (T - \gamma)^{1+\beta} - (-\gamma)^{1+\beta} \} \right]$$

$$\text{Holding Cost} = H \int_0^T I(t) dt = H \int_0^T \left(aP^{-b} \left(\int_t^T e^{\alpha(t-\gamma)^\beta} dt \right) e^{-\alpha(t-\gamma)^\beta} \right) dt$$

$$= HaP^{-b} \left[\frac{T^2}{2} + \frac{\alpha\beta(T - \gamma)^{2+\beta}}{(1 + \beta)(2 + \beta)} + \frac{2\alpha(-\gamma)^{2+\beta}}{(1 + \beta)(2 + \beta)} + \frac{\alpha T(-\gamma)^{1+\beta}}{(1 + \beta)} + \frac{\alpha\gamma(T - \gamma)^{1+\beta}}{(1 + \beta)} \right]$$

(Neglecting the power of ‘ α ’ higher than the first by assuming $0 < \alpha < 1$)

$$\text{Sales revenue} = PD(P)T = aP^{1-b}T.$$

3.1 Solution Procedure:

We find an optimal payment time and replenishment cycle, which maximize the total profit function. Although, the function of total cost is differentiable, the resulting equation is intractable.

First, we find the optimal solution in case-1.

$$TP_1 = aP^{1-b} + I_e aTP^{1-b} \left(TM - \frac{T^2}{2} \right) - \frac{S}{T} - CaP^{-b} \left[T + \frac{\alpha}{1+\beta} \{ (T-\gamma)^{1+\beta} - (-\gamma)^{1+\beta} \} \right] - HaP^{-b} \left[\frac{T}{2} + \frac{\alpha\beta(T-\gamma)^{2+\beta}}{T(1+\beta)(2+\beta)} + \frac{2\alpha(-\gamma)^{2+\beta}}{T(1+\beta)(2+\beta)} + \frac{\alpha(-\gamma)^{1+\beta}}{(1+\beta)} + \frac{\alpha\gamma(T-\gamma)^{1+\beta}}{T(1+\beta)} \right]$$

The necessary conditions for the total profit to be maximum is

$$\frac{\partial TP_1}{\partial T} = 0$$

$$I_e aP^{1-b} \left(2TM - \frac{3T^2}{2} \right) + \frac{S}{T^2} - CaP^{-b} [1 + \alpha(T-\gamma)^\beta] - HaP^{-b} \left[\frac{1}{2} + \frac{\alpha\beta}{(1+\beta)(2+\beta)} \left\{ \frac{(T-\gamma)^{1+\beta}}{T^2} (T(1+\beta) + \gamma) \right\} - \frac{2\alpha(-\gamma)^{2+\beta}}{T^2(1+\beta)(2+\beta)} + \frac{\alpha\gamma}{(1+\beta)} \left\{ \frac{(T-\gamma)^\beta}{T^2} (T\beta + \gamma) \right\} \right] = 0$$

.... (7)

Theorem-1: The sufficient condition for the optimal solution is that the solution (T) must satisfy the following relation:

$$I_e P(2M - 3T) < \frac{2SP^b}{aT^3} + Ca\beta(T-\gamma)^{\beta-1} + H \left[\frac{\alpha\beta}{(1+\beta)(2+\beta)} \left\{ \frac{(1+\beta)(T-\gamma)^{1+\beta}}{T^2} + \frac{(1+\beta)(T-\gamma)^\beta}{T^2} (T(1+\beta) + \gamma) - \frac{2(T-\gamma)^{1+\beta}}{T^3} (T(1+\beta) + \gamma) \right\} - \frac{4\alpha(-\gamma)^{2+\beta}}{T^3(1+\beta)(2+\beta)} + \frac{\alpha\gamma}{(1+\beta)} \left\{ \frac{\beta(T-\gamma)^\beta}{T^2} + \frac{\beta(T-\gamma)^{\beta-1}}{T^2} (T\beta + \gamma) - \frac{2(T-\gamma)^\beta}{T^3} (T\beta + \gamma) \right\} \right]$$

Now, we find the optimal solution in case-2.

The necessary conditions for the total profit to be maximum are

$$\frac{\partial TP}{\partial K} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial TP}{\partial T} = 0$$

That is

$$I_e aP^{-b} \left\{ P + C - \frac{2PK}{T} \right\} - I_p CaP^{-b} \left[1 - \frac{K}{T} + \frac{\alpha(T-M)}{T(1+\beta)} + \frac{\alpha\beta(K-\gamma)^{1+\beta}}{T} - \frac{\alpha(2+\beta)(T-\gamma)}{T(1+\beta)} (K-\gamma)^{1+\beta} \right] = 0$$

.... (8)

and

$$I_e a P^{-b} \left\{ \frac{P}{2} - C + \frac{PK^2}{T^2} \right\} + \frac{S}{T^2} - C a P^{-b} [1 + \alpha(T - \gamma)^\beta] - H a P^{-b} \left[\frac{1}{2} + \frac{\alpha\beta(T-\gamma)^{1+\beta}(2+\gamma+\beta-T)}{T^2(1+\beta)(2+\beta)} - \frac{2\alpha(-\gamma)^{2+\beta}}{T^2(1+\beta)(2+\beta)} + \frac{\alpha\gamma(T-\gamma)^\beta(1+\gamma+\beta-T)}{T^2(1+\beta)} \right] - I_p C a P^{-b} \left[\frac{1}{2T^2} (K^2 - M^2) + \frac{\alpha(K-M)M}{T^2(1+\beta)} - \frac{\alpha\beta}{T^2(2+\beta)} \{ (K - \gamma)^{2+\beta} - (M - \gamma)^{2+\beta} \} - \frac{\alpha\gamma}{T^2(1+\beta)} \{ (K - \gamma)^{2+\beta} - (M - \gamma)^{2+\beta} \} \right] = 0 \quad \dots (9)$$

On solving the above two equation, we get the values of (K, T).

Theorem-2: The sufficient condition for the optimal solution is that the solution (K, T) must satisfy the following relation:

$$I_p C [1 + \alpha(K - \gamma)^\beta \{ (2 + \beta)(T - \gamma) - \beta(1 + \beta) \}] < 2I_e P$$

And

$$2I_e P K^2 + \frac{2SP^b}{a} + C [1 + \alpha\beta(T - \gamma)^{1+\beta}] + H \left[\frac{\alpha\beta \{ T((2+\gamma+\beta-T)(1+\beta)(T-\gamma)^\beta - (T-\gamma)^{1+\beta}) - 2(T-\gamma)^{1+\beta}(2+\gamma+\beta-T) \}}{(1+\beta)(2+\beta)} + \frac{4\alpha(-\gamma)^{2+\beta}}{(1+\beta)(2+\beta)} + \frac{\alpha\gamma \{ T((1+\gamma+\beta-T)(\beta)(T-\gamma)^{\beta-1} - (T-\gamma)^\beta) - 2(T-\gamma)^\beta(1+\gamma+\beta-T) \}}{(1+\beta)} \right] + I_p C a P^{-b} \left[-(K^2 - M^2) - \frac{2\alpha(K-M)M}{(1+\beta)} - 2\alpha \{ (K - \gamma)^{2+\beta} - (M - \gamma)^{2+\beta} \} \left\{ \frac{\beta}{2+\beta} + \frac{\gamma}{1+\beta} \right\} \right] > 0$$

Hence, if the solution (K, T) satisfies above inequalities and the constraint $M \leq K \leq T$ then the optimal solution (K^*, T^*) is obtained.

3.2 Solution Algorithm:

We follow the following algorithm to obtain the optimal value of optimal payment time and replenishment cycle.

Step-1: If Theorem-1 holds than the optimal value of replenishment cycle can be obtained from equation (7) otherwise go to the step-2.

Step-2: On solving equation (8) and (9), we get the values of (K,T).

Step-3: If the solution satisfies Theorem-2 and the condition $M \leq K \leq T$ then the present solution is optimal solution.

4. Numerical Example:

We consider the following example to illustrate the feasibility of proposed model and the sensitivity analysis of the optimal solution to change in the values of different parameters. Following data for the analysis has been taken from the literature:

We set the different ordering cost $S=\$5, 10, 15, 20, 25$ per order, $P=\$30$ per unit, $a=15*10^5$, $b=3$, $H=\$0.12$ per unit, $C=\$20$ per unit, $\alpha=0.05$, $\beta=2$, $\gamma=2.5$, $I_p=0.09/\$/\text{year}$, $I_e=0.06/\$/\text{year}$, $M=30$ days= 0.082192years . We present the optimal solution in Table-1.

5. Sensitivity Analysis:

We now study the effect of changes in the system parameters $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, a, b, C, H$ and K on the optimal total profit. The sensitive analysis is performed by changing each of the parameters by 40%, 20%, -20% and -40% and taking one parameter at a time and keeping the others parameters unchanged. On the basis of the results of Table-2, the following observation can be made:

1. Model is highly sensitive with respect to all parameters except holding cost.
2. Feasible solution does not exist in most of the case as the value of β varies.
3. As the value of α increase, the optimal payment time, replenishment cycle as well as the profit of the system.
4. The value of γ, a, H, S, K, T and TP are positively related whereas the K, T and TP are negatively correlated with 'b'.
5. $K, T,$ and TP are highly sensitive to the changes in the value of 'b'. Special attention must be pay while calculating the value of 'b' as 'b' increases the value of the system decreases whereas it increases as the value of 'b' decreases. Thus, from this analysis we can say that necessary steps should be taken to estimate the value of the parameter 'b' while conducting case studies.
6. As the trade credit period increases, optimal payment time and total profit of the system increases whereas the replenishment cycle time decreases.

Table-1: Optimal Solution for Different Value of S:

S (\$)	(K*, T*)
5	(30, 17)
10	(30, 25)
15	(33, 50)
20	(37, 56)
25	(40,61)

Table-2: Sensitive Analysis with respect to different parameters:

Parameters	% Change	K*(%)	T*(%)	TP*(%)
	-40%	-11.04	-23.56	-33.77

A	-20%	-6.68	-12.34	-20.89
	20%	7.34	13.39	20.86
	40%	11.78	24.56	32.54
B	-40%	36.98	66.78	0.026
	-20%	28.66	54.65	0.015
	20%	-26.67	-52.55	-0.01
Γ	40%	-38.96	-68.77	-0.02
	-40%	-20.56	-41.98	-45.67
	-20%	-7.89	-12.75	-33.59
Γ	20%	6.76	11.67	37.98
	40%	19.45	39.89	49.56
	-40%	-15.89	-33.78	--68.99
A	-20%	-9.05	-17.89	-45.67
	20%	11.89	19.56	48.98
	40%	17.09	35.98	65.87
B	-40%	16.98	39.09	67.90
	-20%	9.08	19.03	45.89
	20%	-10.23	-20.91	-42.94
B	40%	-19.67	-40.98	-65.93
	-40%	-0.02	-0.39	4.69
	-20%	-0.01	-0.15	2.01
H	20%	0.01	0.16	-2.14
	40%	0.03	0.41	-4.23
	-40%	-11.03	-35.67	35.67
S	-20%	-9.67	-15.24	25.89
	20%	11.25	11.56	-11.35
	40%	21.14	21.46	-29.54
M	-40%	-12.56	31.89	-37.45
	-20%	-6.09	12.34	-13.25
	20%	6.89	-11.98	14.01
M	40%	13.02	-30.98	41.98

6. Conclusion:

The main purpose of this study is to formulate a deterministic inventory model for deteriorating items with selling price-dependent demand rate and trade credit period under three-parameter Weibull distribution deterioration rate. In real-life situation, suppliers always

offer a trade credit period to their retailers. As a result, an inventory model for deteriorating items with selling price dependent demand to determine the optimal payment time and optimal replenishment has been developed. Numerical example is studied to illustrate the model and sensitivity analysis also carried out to check the behavior of model with respect to different parameters. It is seen from the table-1, that few parameters are positively correlated with optimal payment time and replenishment cycle whereas rest are negatively correlated. The proposed model can be applied for IC packaging factory where molding compound are required whose consumption rate depends on the stock and the deterioration rate resulting from inappropriate storage, temperature and expiration date.

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